

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT & VALIDATION OF
DICYCLOMINE HCL AND PARACETAMOL BY RP-HPLC****Gannoju Vasundhara, Koppu Udaya Bhanu Sri*, Dr.D. Venkata Ramana, Dr. G. Sai Kiran.**¹department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Holy Mary Institute Of Technology And Science
(College Of Pharmacy), Kondapur, Telangana.**Abstract:**

An analytical method for the simultaneous estimation of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride (HCL) and Paracetamol in pharmaceutical dosage forms was developed and validated using Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC). The method was optimized to ensure efficient separation and accurate quantification of both drugs. The Waters HPLC system equipped with an auto-sampler and PDA Detector 996 model was used, employing a Phenomenex Gemini C18 column (4.6 mm × 150 mm, 5.0 μm particle size). The mobile phase consisted of methanol and TEA buffer (pH 4.8) in a 32:68 (v/v) ratio, and the column temperature was maintained at 38°C. The method utilized a flow rate of 1 mL/min and detection at a wavelength of 248 nm. The injection volume was 20 μL, and the total run time was 7 minutes. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for parameters such as specificity, accuracy, precision, linearity, and robustness. The results demonstrated the method's suitability for the routine analysis of Dicyclomine HCL and Paracetamol in pharmaceutical formulations, offering a fast, reliable, and cost-effective approach for quality control in the pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: Dicyclomine Hydrochloride (HCL) and Paracetamol, RP-HPLC, Simultaneous Estimation, Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms, Waters HPLC.

Corresponding author:**Koppu Udaya Bhanu Sri ***

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
Holy Mary Institute of Technology and Science,
Kondapur, Telangana.

Email Id- bhanusri51@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Koppu Udaya Bhanu Sri et al., *Analytical Method Development & Validation Of Dicyclomine Hcl And Paracetamol By RP-HPLC*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12 (01).

INTRODUCTION:

1.1 Chromatography

1.1.1 Introduction

The chromatography was discovered by Russian Chemist and botanist *Micheal Tswett* (1872-1919) who first used the term chromatography (colour writing derived from Greek for colour – Chroma, and write – graphein) to describe his work on the separation of coloured plant pigments into bands on a column of chalk and other material such as polysaccharides, sucrose and insulin.

“*Chromatography is a method in which the components of a mixture are separated on an adsorbent column in a flowing system*”.

The adsorbent material, or stationary phase, first described by Russian scientist named Tswett in 1906, has taken many forms over the years, including paper, thin layers of solids attached to glass plates, immobilized liquids, gels, and solid particles packed in columns.

“Chromatography is a physical method of separation in which the component to be separated are distributed between two phases of which in stationary while other moves in a definite direction (IUPAC)”

1.1.2. Types of Chromatography

The mobile phase could be either a liquid or a gas, and accordingly we can subdivide chromatography into Liquid Chromatography (LC) or Gas Chromatography (GC). Apart from these methods, there are two other modes that use a liquid mobile phase, but the nature of its transport through the porous stationary phase is in the form of either (a) capillary forces, as in planar chromatography (also called Thin-Layer Chromatography, TLC), or (b) electro osmotic flow, as in the case of Capillary Electro Chromatography (CEC).

1. Adsorption chromatography

Chromatography in which separation is based mainly on difference between the adsorption affinities of the sample components for the surface of an active solid. The analyte interact with solid stationary surface and are displaced with eluent for active sites on surface.

2. Partition chromatography

This method results from a thermodynamic distribution of analytes between two liquid phases. On the basis of relative polarities of stationary and mobile phase, partition chromatography can be divided in to normal phase and reverse phase chromatography. In normal phase chromatography, the stationary phase bed is strongly polar in nature (e.g. Silica gel) and the mobile phase is non-polar (such as n-hexane or tetrahydrofuran). Polar sample are thus retained on polar surface of the column packing longer than polar material while in reverse phase chromatography, the stationary bed is non-polar (hydrophobic in nature, while the mobile phase is polar liquid, such as mixture

of water and methanol or Acetonitrile. Here the more non polar the material is, the longer it will retain.

3. Size-exclusion chromatography

This involves a solid stationary phase with controlled pore size. Solids are separated according to molecular size, with the large molecule unable to enter the pores eluted first.

4. Ion- exchange chromatography

Involves a solid stationary phase with anionic or cationic groups on the surface to separation, HPLC and HPTLC methods have widely been exploited in pharmaceutical analysis because of its simplicity, precision, accuracy and reproducibility of result.

5. Solid-Phase Extraction [SPE]

A sample preparation technique that uses LC principles to isolate, enriches, and/or purifies analytes from a complex matrix applied to a miniature chromatographic bed. *Offline* SPE is done with larger particles in individual plastic cartridges or in micro-elution plate wells, using low positive pressure or vacuum to assist flow. *Online* SPE is done with smaller particles in miniature HPLC columns using higher pressures and a valve to switch the SPE column online with the primary HPLC column, or offline to waste, as appropriate. SPE methods use step gradients to accomplish bed conditioning, sample loading, washing, and elution steps. The goal is to remove matrix interferences and to isolate the analyte in a solution, and at a concentration, suitable for subsequent analysis.

1.2.1. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)⁶

The acronym *HPLC*, coined by the Late Prof. Csaba Horvath for his 1970 Pittconpaper, originally indicated the fact that high pressure was used to generate the flow required for liquid chromatography in packed columns. In the beginning, pumps only had a pressure capability of 500 psi [35 bars]. This was called *high pressure liquid chromatography*, or HPLC. The early 1970s saw a tremendous leap in technology. These new HPLC instruments could develop up to 6,000 psi [400 bars] of pressure, and incorporated improved injectors, detectors, and columns. With continued advances in performance during this time [smaller particles, even higher pressure], the acronym HPLC remained the same, but the name was changed to high performance liquid chromatography.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography is now one of the most powerful tools in analytical chemistry. It has the ability to separate, identify, and quantitative the compounds that are present in any sample that can be dissolved in a liquid. Today, compounds in trace concentrations as low as *parts per trillion* (ppt) may easily be identified. HPLC can be, and has been, applied to just about any sample, such as

pharmaceuticals, food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics, environmental matrices, forensic samples, and industrial chemicals.

1.2.4. Reversed phase chromatography (RPC)

Reversed phase HPLC (RP-HPLC) consists of a non-polar stationary phase and an aqueous, moderately polar mobile phase. One common stationary phase is silica which has been treated with RMe_2SiCl , where R is a straight chain alkyl group such as $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{37}$ or C_8H_{17} . The retention time is therefore longer for molecules which are more non-polar in nature, allowing polar molecules to elute more readily. Retention Time (R_t) is increased by the addition of polar solvent to the mobile phase and decreased by the addition of more hydrophobic solvent. The pharmaceutical industry regularly employs RPC to qualify drugs before their release.

RPC operates on the principle of hydrophobic interactions, which result from repulsive forces between a polar eluent, the relatively non-polar analyte, and the non-polar stationary phase. The binding of the analyte to the stationary phase is proportional to the contact surface area around the non-polar segment of the analyte molecule upon association with the ligand in the aqueous eluent. The energy released in this process is proportional to the surface tension of the eluent (water: 73 erg/cm^2 , methanol: 22 erg/cm^2) and to the hydrophobic surface of the analyte and the ligand respectively. The retention can be decreased by adding less-polar solvent (MeOH, ACN) into the mobile phase to reduce the surface tension of water. Gradient elution uses this effect by automatically changing the polarity of the mobile phase during the course of the analysis.

A separation in which the mobile phase composition remains constant throughout the procedure is termed isocratic (meaning constant composition). The word was coined by Csaba Horvath, who was one of the pioneers of HPLC. The mobile phase composition does not have to remain constant. A separation in which the mobile phase composition is changed during the separation process is described as a gradient elution. One example is a gradient starting at 10% methanol and ending at 90% methanol after 20 minutes. The two components of the mobile phase are typically termed "A" and "B"; A is the "weak" solvent which allows the solute to elute only slowly, while B

is the "strong" solvent which rapidly elutes the solutes from the column. In reverse-phase chromatography, solvent A is often water or an aqueous buffer, while B is an organic solvent miscible with water, such as Acetonitrile, methanol, THF, or isopropanol.

1.2.6. Working Principle of HPLC⁸

The components of a basic High-Performance Liquid Chromatography [HPLC] system are shown in the simple diagram in figure 5. A reservoir holds the solvent [called the mobile phase, because it moves]. A high-pressure pump [solvent delivery system or solvent manager] is used to generate and meter a specified flow rate of mobile phase, typically millilitres per minute. An injector is able to introduce [inject] the sample into the continuously flowing mobile phase stream that carries the sample into the HPLC column.

The column contains the chromatographic packing material needed to effect the separation. This packing material is called the stationary phase because it is held in place by the column hardware. A detector is needed to see the separated compound bands as they elute from the HPLC column. The mobile phase exits the detector and can be sent to waste, or collected, as desired. When the mobile phase contains a separated compound band, HPLC provides the ability to collect this fraction of the elute containing that purified compound for further study. This is called preparative chromatography.

The detector is wired to the computer data station, the HPLC system component that records the electrical signal needed to generate the chromatogram on its display and to identify and quantitative the concentration of the sample constituents. Since sample compound characteristics can be very different, several types of detectors have been developed. For example, if a compound can absorb Ultra Violet light, a UV-absorbance detector is used. If the compound does not have either of these characteristics, a more universal type of detector is used, such as an Evaporative-Light-Scattering Detector [ELSD]. The most powerful approach is the use multiple detectors in series. For example, a UV and/or ELSD detector may be used in combination with a Mass Spectrometer [MS] to analyze the results of the chromatographic separation. This provides, from a single injection, more comprehensive information about an analyte. The practice of coupling a mass spectrometer to an HPLC system is called LC/MS.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

INSTRUMENTS USED

HPLC from WATERS, software: Empower 2, Alliance 2695 separation module. 996 PDA detector.

CHEMICALS USED:

Dicyclomine HCl and Paracetamol from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK) and Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck.

METHOD VALIDATION**PREPARATION OF MOBILE PHASE:****Preparation of mobile phase:**

Accurately measured 320ml (32%) of HPLC Methanol and 680ml of TEA buffer (68%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**(Optimized Chromatogram):**

Column : Phenomenex Gemini C18
(4.6mm \times 150mm, 5.0 μ m) particle size
Column temperature : 38°C
Wavelength : 248nm
Mobile phase ratio : Methanol: TEA
buffer pH 4.8 (32:68v/v)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Injection volume : 20 μ l
Run time : 7minutes

Figure-: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table-: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	859856	42569	1.24	7896	6.8
2	Paracetamol	5.405	5698	3652	1.36	6582	

Observation: From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Dicyclomine HCl and Paracetamol peaks are well separated and they show proper retention time, resolution, peak tail and plate count. So it's optimized trial.

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Figure-: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Table-: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.222	865898	43659	1.26	7985	7.0
2	Paracetamol	5.453	5789	3785	1.38	6659	

Acceptance Criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2.
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000.
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

METHOD VALIDATION**System Suitability:****Table-: Results of system Suitability for Dicyclomine HCl**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.200	859865	42568	7895	1.24
2	Dicyclomine HCl	3.248	859788	42587	7859	1.24
3	Dicyclomine HCl	3.299	857984	42659	7869	1.24
4	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	854879	42875	7849	1.24
5	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	857896	42487	7859	1.23
Mean			858082.4			
Std. Dev.			2024.409			
% RSD			0.235922			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table-: Results of System Suitability for Paracetamol

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Paracetamol	5.413	5689	3659	6583	1.36
2	Paracetamol	5.484	5687	3648	6592	1.37
3	Paracetamol	5.405	5682	3698	6549	1.37
4	Paracetamol	5.405	5649	3675	6571	1.36
5	Paracetamol	5.409	5674	3649	6529	1.36
Mean			5676.2			
Std. Dev.			16.2696			
% RSD			0.286628			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

SPECIFICITY

The ICH documents define specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components.

Analytical method was tested for specificity to measure accurately quantitate Dicyclomine HCl and Paracetamol in drug product.

Assay (Standard):**Table-: Peak Results for Assay Standard****Dicyclomine HCl**

S.No.	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.211	859785	42598	1.25	7856
2	Dicyclomine HCl	3.222	859865	42895	1.24	7859
3	Dicyclomine HCl	3.254	857849	42578	1.25	7869

Paracetamol

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Paracetamol	5.414	5699	3685	1.36	6598	6.9
2	Paracetamol	5.453	5687	3659	1.37	6537	6.9
3	Paracetamol	5.424	5689	3649	1.36	6582	7.0

Assay (Sample):**Table-: Peak Results for Assay sample****Dicyclomine HCl**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	865985	43659	1.26	7985
2	Dicyclomine HCl	3.294	865798	43875	1.26	7925
3	Dicyclomine HCl	3.295	865456	43659	1.27	7946

Paracetamol

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Paracetamol	5.435	5789	3659	1.37	6659	6.9
2	Paracetamol	5.417	5798	3684	1.38	6689	7.0
3	Paracetamol	5.434	5749	3695	1.38	6648	6.9

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Dicyclomine HCl and Paracetamol in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.82%.

LINEARITY**CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR LINEARITY STUDY:****Dicyclomine HCl**

Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Average Peak Area
18	1789546
24	2456987
30	3085985
36	3759864
42	4406589

Fig-: Calibration Curve of Dicyclomine HCl

LINEARITY PLOT:

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Dicyclomine HCl is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 10515$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 45591$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.999$$

VALIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 45591. These values meet the validation criteria.

PARACETAMOL

Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Average Peak Area
10	2038
20	3859
30	5698
40	7489
50	9218

Fig-: Calibration Curve of Paracetamol

LINEARITY PLOT:

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Paracetamol is a straight line.

Correlation Coefficient (r) = 0.999

VALIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99. These values meet the validation criteria.

PRECISION:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

REPEATABILITY

Obtained Five (5) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Table-: Results of Repeatability for Dicyclomine HCl :

S. No.	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.213	859856	42659	7859	1.24
2	Dicyclomine HCl	3.253	857985	42598	7869	1.24
3	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	856984	42587	7846	1.25
4	Dicyclomine HCl	3.215	856987	42569	7819	1.25
5	Dicyclomine HCl	3.254	859878	42894	7856	1.24
Mean			858338			
Std.dev			1454.222			
%RSD			0.169423			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise

Table-: Results of repeatability for Paracetamol:

S. No.	Peak Name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Paracetamol	5.441	5697	3659	6592	1.36
2	Paracetamol	5.442	5689	3648	6539	1.36
3	Paracetamol	5.409	5698	3692	6584	1.37
4	Paracetamol	5.520	5639	3648	6579	1.36
5	Paracetamol	5.424	5688	3689	6549	1.36
Mean			5682.2			
Std.dev			24.57031			
%RSD			0.432408			

Intermediate precision:**Day 1:****Table-: Results of Intermediate precision for Dicyclomine HCl**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.211	868956	43659	7985	1.26
2	Dicyclomine HCl	3.211	869857	43985	7954	1.27
3	Dicyclomine HCl	3.210	865983	43879	7946	1.26
4	Dicyclomine HCl	3.212	866587	43865	7963	1.27
5	Dicyclomine HCl	3.211	864256	43875	7964	1.26
6	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	868974	43562	7942	1.26
Mean			867435.5			
Std. Dev.			2167.095			
% RSD			0.249828			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Table-: Results of Intermediate precision for Paracetamol

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Paracetamol	5.411	5785	3789	6659	1.37
2	Paracetamol	5.410	5798	3758	6625	1.38
3	Paracetamol	5.420	5766	3746	6649	1.38
4	Paracetamol	5.423	5746	3795	6675	1.37
5	Paracetamol	5.419	5782	3761	6653	1.38
6	Paracetamol	5.409	5786	3752	6627	1.37
Mean			5777.167			
Std. Dev.			18.40018			
% RSD			0.318498			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Day 2:**Table-: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Dicyclomine HCl**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine HCl	3.211	845985	44585	8025	1.27
2	Dicyclomine HCl	3.233	847895	44895	8069	1.28
3	Dicyclomine HCl	3.244	848985	44758	8046	1.27

4	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	847859	44548	8094	1.28
5	Dicyclomine HCl	3.297	845984	44865	8042	1.28
6	Dicyclomine HCl	3.202	847898	44254	8076	1.27
Mean			847434.3			
Std. Dev.			1201.345			
% RSD			0.141763			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Table:- Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Paracetamol

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V} \cdot \text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Paracetamol	5.411	5898	3986	6852	1.39
2	Paracetamol	5.410	5884	3955	6864	1.39
3	Paracetamol	5.420	5863	3956	6829	1.40
4	Paracetamol	5.405	5845	3945	6874	1.39
5	Paracetamol	5.409	5896	3925	6829	1.39
6	Paracetamol	5.463	5874	3962	6825	1.40
Mean			5876.667			
Std. Dev.			20.39281			
% RSD			0.347013			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

6.3.4: ACCURACY:

Accuracy at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) was prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Table:- The accuracy results for Dicyclomine HCl

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	451144.3	25	24.998	99.992%	100.1873%
100%	897248.3	50	50.104	100.208%	
150%	1344562	75	75.278	100.362%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Table:- The accuracy Results for Paracetamol

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	2895	15	15.084	100.560%	100.748%
100%	5685.333	30	30.282	100.940%	
150%	8449	45	45.335	100.744%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Dicyclomine HCl :

Result: =2.6 μ g/ml

Paracetamol:

Result: =3.4 μ g/ml

Quantitation limit

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Dicyclomine HCl:

Result: =7.8 μ g/ml

Paracetamol:

Result: =10.2 μ g/ml

ROBUSTNESS

The robustness was performed for the flow rate variations from 0.9 ml/min to 1.1ml/min and mobile phase ratio variation from more organic phase to less organic phase ratio for Dicyclomine HCl and Paracetamol. The method is robust only in less flow condition and the method is robust even by change in the Mobile phase $\pm 5\%$. The standard sample of Dicyclomine HCl and Paracetamol were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor and plate count.

Variation in flow

Figure: Chromatogram showing less flow of 0.9ml/min

Figure:- Chromatogram showing more flow of 1.1 ml/min

Variation of mobile phase organic composition

Figure: Chromatogram showing less organic composition

Figure: Chromatogram showing more organic composition

Table: Results for Robustness

Dicyclomine HCl

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	859856	3.297	7896	1.24
Less Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	915847	3.639	7251	1.20
More Flow rate of 1.1mL/min	842564	2.859	7415	1.21
Less organic phase (about 5 % decrease in organic phase)	825498	3.460	7365	1.23
More organic phase (about 5 % Increase in organic phase)	814578	3.022	7258	1.22

Acceptance Criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Table: Results for Robustness

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Paracetamol Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.1mL/min	5698	5.405	6582	1.36
Less Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	6452	6.250	6785	1.32
More Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	5254	4.863	6365	1.34
Less organic phase (about 5 % decrease in organic phase)	5487	6.196	6254	1.38
More organic phase (about 5 % Increase in organic phase)	5369	5.010	6298	1.33

Acceptance Criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Summary

An RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Dicyclomine Hydrochloride (HCL) and Paracetamol in

pharmaceutical dosage forms. The method was optimized using a Waters HPLC system with an auto-sampler and PDA Detector 996 model, with a Phenomenex Gemini C18 column (4.6 mm × 150 mm, 5.0 μm particle size). The chromatographic conditions

included a mobile phase of methanol and TEA buffer (pH 4.8) in a 32:68 (v/v) ratio, a column temperature of 38°C, a flow rate of 1 mL/min, and detection at 248 nm. The injection volume was 20 µL, and the total run time was 7 minutes. The method was validated following ICH guidelines, confirming its accuracy, precision, specificity, linearity, and robustness. The method was successfully applied for the simultaneous analysis of both drugs in their combined dosage forms, offering a rapid and efficient solution for pharmaceutical quality control.

CONCLUSION:

The RP-HPLC method developed for the simultaneous estimation of Dicyclomine HCL and Paracetamol is efficient, reliable, and validated for routine pharmaceutical analysis. The optimized chromatographic conditions provide clear separation of both drugs within a short analysis time of 7 minutes. The validation results demonstrated the method's accuracy, precision, and robustness, making it suitable for quality control testing of Dicyclomine HCL and Paracetamol in pharmaceutical formulations. The developed method is cost-effective and can be used in routine quality assurance and regulatory testing in the pharmaceutical industry.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Authors are thankful to the Management and Principal, Department of Pharmacy, Holy Mary Institute of Technology and science (College of Pharmacy) in Kondapur, Telangana, for extending support to carry out the research work. Finally, the authors express their gratitude to the Sura Pharma Labs, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, for providing research equipment and facilities.

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